

FORMATION OF EDUCATIONAL MOTIVATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS BY MEANS OF INTERACTIVE METHODS

Turumbetova Aygul Yusupbayevna

Teacher of Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

turumbetova88@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14514111>

Abstract. In this thesis, in order to prepare for the effective organization of classes in primary classes, to form students' learning motivation, the opinions of students on independent study and learning, critical and creative approach to them, and free thinking are noted.

Keywords: elementary school, independent study, critical thinking, creative approach, free thinking, learning motivation.

INTRODUCTION

The formation of educational motivation is one of the most pressing issues in modern pedagogy, particularly at the primary school level. Motivation serves as the driving force behind a student's engagement, effort, and persistence in learning activities. At the primary stage of education, children develop their foundational attitudes toward learning, which impact their academic success and lifelong learning habits. Traditional teaching methods often fall short of maintaining young learners' interest and enthusiasm. Therefore, the use of **interactive methods** has emerged as a powerful tool for fostering and sustaining educational motivation in primary school students. This article explores the role of interactive methods in enhancing educational motivation among young learners, focusing on their effectiveness, practical applications, and pedagogical benefits.

The change of priorities in the national education system, the search for the conditions of subject-subject interaction of the participants of the pedagogical process, sets the most important task of developing positive and stable motivation of students. When the interest in the subjective component of the educational process on the basis of the new educational strategy based on the competence approach is increasing, the attitude towards the result of education and the process of determining the student's personal destiny has changed. Educational activity is such an activity, as a result of which, first of all, a change occurs in the student. Its product should be viewed based on different motives. These motives should be directly related to the growth and development of the student's personality. In order to prepare for the effective organization of

reading classes in primary school, classes in reading classes can be organized in the methods of independent work and research, in the method of brainstorming.

MAIN PART

Educational motivation refers to the internal or external factors that drive a student to engage in learning activities. It includes intrinsic motivation (learning for joy and satisfaction) and extrinsic motivation (learning for rewards or recognition). For primary school students, intrinsic motivation plays a significant role as their curiosity and excitement about learning are still fresh and uninhibited.

Key components of educational motivation in young children include:

Interest in subject matter: Enjoyment derived from engaging and meaningful activities.

Positive reinforcement: Receiving praise and recognition from teachers and parents.

Sense of achievement: Accomplishing tasks boosts confidence and self-worth.

Interactive environment: Engaging with peers and the teacher to create a dynamic learning process.

The absence of motivation can lead to disengagement, lack of participation, and, ultimately, poor academic performance. Interactive methods aim to directly address this challenge by creating a stimulating and collaborative classroom environment.

Interactive methods involve active participation, collaboration, and dialogue among students and teachers. These methods shift the focus from passive learning (lectures and rote memorization) to active learning, where students are encouraged to explore, question, and discover knowledge independently or collaboratively.

Benefits of interactive methods include:

Active engagement: Students become central participants in the learning process.

Socialization: Collaboration enhances communication, teamwork, and social skills.

Critical thinking: Problem-solving tasks and open-ended discussions foster analytical thinking.

Individualization: Activities can be tailored to meet diverse learning needs.

Joyful learning environment: Fun and interactive lessons maintain students' interest and motivation.

The purpose of the subject and the lesson is to teach students to read and learn the artistic features of literary genres such as stories, fairy tales, poems, parables taught at school, to be able to independently analyze the work, to understand its content and idea. It is said that it is mastery, reading skills, acquisition of speech culture. Organizing and conducting the lesson in this way will greatly help students to read and study literature independently, approach them critically and creatively, and think freely. constitutes The speech is coherent, expressive, not grammatical rules, but is formed enough to exchange ideas with others according to the quantity and scope. Along with this, there is also an internal aspect of the child's mental preparation for school education. By this time, he will have a correct idea about acquiring knowledge, reading and learning. He tends to obey the school discipline and follow the instructions of the teachers. But since children's abilities and talents are not the same, important differences arise between them. Therefore, some children go to school with great enthusiasm, while some go to the point of refusing school. It is important to fight in school education so that the student does not have a negative attitude towards studying. The most appropriate way in this work is an individual approach, taking into account the uniqueness of the level of knowledge in children. Theoretical studies and school experience developed to date show that motivation is a variety of motives, needs, interests, aspirations, goals, aspirations, motivational attitudes or inclinations, ideals, etc. broad meaning refers to defining behavior in general. The study and generalization of the conclusions about the nature of positive stable motivation available in psychological and pedagogical research made it possible to form the main definition used in the research process. The effectiveness of teaching in primary classes has shown that there are untapped opportunities. These opportunities are first of all inextricably linked with the improvement of teaching methods, support and formation of students' interest in learning. Pedagogical and psychological studies have shown that interest in reading has a great impact on the motivation of children aged 6-11, and has a positive effect on the resulting learning results. The ability to systematically support games of various contents in improving the effectiveness of reading allows a person not only to learn to apply knowledge by the teacher, but also to educate some personal qualities that play an important role in their overall development. That's why we made the problem of organizing and conducting the analysis of bees in primary classes the subject of our graduation work.

Usually, the real psychological nature of learning and teaching activity cannot be imagined without the cooperation of the student and the teacher. The analysis of the essence and main factors that determine the manifestation of positive stable motivation in elementary grades allows us to confirm the following: educational motivation is characterized by a complex structure as a specific motivation, one of its forms is the structure of internal and external motivation; important features such as the stability of positive motivation, the level of intellectual development and the nature of educational activities;

The main factors preventing the manifestation of positive motivation are: failure avoidance, personal anxiety, low evaluation, external attribution; the main determinants of a person's educational activity are achievement motivation and some characteristics of the person, first of all, autonomy; positive sustainable motivation is determined by several factors specific to this activity.

Firstly: it is related to the structure of the educational system and the type of educational institution, in this case, the school where educational activities are carried out;

Secondly: organization of the training course;

Thirdly: the subjective characteristics of the student;

Fourth: the subjective characteristics of the teacher's interaction with schoolchildren and, first of all, the system of his relationship with the student; The mechanism of formation of positive and stable motivation of educational activities in the school educational process consists of the main stages: setting the goal, determining the structure of the educational movement, operational-cognitive, reasonable selection of organizational forms of work, activity-operational, reflection, evaluation of the activities of adolescents .

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, as a result of the implementation of positive stable motivation for educational activity in the educational process at school, positive stable motivation for educational activity due to need in high school students: intellectual self-awareness in the classroom, group study skills and competencies, willingness to self-assess abilities, satisfaction with training and success in the classroom. Interactive methods play a pivotal role in shaping educational motivation among primary school students. By actively engaging children in the learning process through games, group work, technology, and project-based learning, educators can create a dynamic and stimulating classroom environment. These methods not only maintain students' interest and

enthusiasm but also develop essential skills such as teamwork, critical thinking, and creativity. Teachers, as facilitators of this approach, must be equipped with the necessary skills and resources to effectively implement interactive methods. The long-term benefits of fostering motivation at an early stage are profound, leading to a generation of confident, enthusiastic, and lifelong learners.

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